

MODERN SIGNS OF USING THE QUINCE PLANT IN FOLK MEDICINE

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Annotation: It was decided to write this article so that future doctors need to use natural products in the medicine, give up chemicals, use environmentally friendly, centuries-old tried and tested methods of treatment. This article talks about the use of the plant of Quince in medicine and cosmetology on the basis of folk medicine.

Keywords: folk medicine, quince, natural, cosmetology, disease, treatment, fruit, leaf, seed, medicinal, immunity, tea, infusion, decoction.

Introduction

Bene dignoscitur, bene curatur.

Quince –(Cydonia,ae,f) is a fruit tree or shrub in the family Rosaceae. Quince is found in wild species in Azerbaijan, Dagestan, Turkmenistan, Iran, in Turkish it was kept under the name of ayva. Quince is widespread in the Caucasus, Central Asia, Crimea, southern Ukraine and the Astrakhan Region of Russia. 80% of the quince growing areas in Uzbekistan are located in the Fergana Valley. The height of the quince is 5-6 meters, the branches are pyramidal, sometimes grow branched, the leaves are simple, green, the edge is whole, the flowers are solitary, white or light pink, bloom in April, when the seedling is planted, enters the crop in 3-4 years, lives 30-40 years, adult trees weigh an average of 60-70 kg. yields. Its fruit is plucked in September-October; weight, 150-500 grams, depending on the variety. The fruits of the quince are lemon-colored or orange-colored, sprinkled with fruit feather; when ripe the fruit feather shed, the fragrant, fresh fruit is consumed sparingly. Quince is an entomophilous (entomophilus, insect pollinated) plant. Quince contains 74.7-83.5% water, 8.5-15.2% sugars (6.2% fructose), around 5% pectin and 0.6% additives, more than 3% organic (apple, wine and lemon) acids, essential oil, 10-20 mg vitamin C, iron, copper, salts, rock cell and other compounds. Quince's seed contains up to 20% mucus, 0.58% amygdaline glycoside, 8.15% fat, and other compounds. Quince's fruit is rough.

Work and research with literatures

The importance of Quince in folk medicine:

Folk medicine uses quince fruit (fructus Cydoniae), quince seed (semen Cydoniae), quince leaf (folium Cydoniae) and quince pustlock (cortex Cydoniae). In ancient times, healers recommended treatment with quince juice against infertility (impotentia). For example today it can be marked like this: quince juice (syrup Cydoniae) drink a tablespoon every evening for 20 days from the moment the new moon comes out.

Bronchial asthma (Asthma bronchiale) is a cure to relieve and even stop an attack. For example: 5gr. quince leaf put 1 liter of boiling water and boil over low heat for 15 minutes, let it brew and squeeze out the leaves. Drink 2 tablespoons 3-4 times a day before meals.

In dry cough (tussis sicca) and colds (frigora): cut one quince in half and separate it from its seeds. 100-150 ml in a separate container. mix with water and put on fire, simmer over medium heat until it looks darker, bring from the heat to a warm state and insist 1 tablespoon before meals in 1 day. Let the tincture be prepared anew every day.

Tea from the seeds and leaves of Quince (*Thea ex foliorum et seminum Cydoniae*) is used as a lead-driving agent (remedium diureticum) in diseases of kidney inflammation (nephritis). For example: take 1 tablespoon of the dried leaf of Quince, take 1 tablespoon of the seed and top with 200 ml. pour boiling water, boil over low heat for 5-6 minutes, strain and pass through gauze, add honey according to taste, drink 1 spoon 3-4 times in 1 day.

In loss of appetite (anorexia): let the fruit of the every other day half quince be steamed with less butter and honey to taste, consumed as a dessert after eating.

When immunity decreases (hyponosia): juice 3 quince fruits straight. Mix with honey according to taste, take little by little throughout the day. Helps to strengthen immunity.

Quince juice with honey as a laxative agent (remedium laxans) in constipation (constipatio) prevents constipation. If inflammation of the urinary tract and bladder (cystitis) is tormented, 50-80 gr in 1 day. heat freshly squeezed quince juice.

The beneficial substances contained in it improve the excretion of urine and have the property of fighting bacteria.

Against anemia (anaemia): clean medium-sized Quince from seeds, fill with 2 teaspoons of honey, then put in a gas oven for 15 minutes and cook softened. It is enough to eat honey with Quince 1 time in 1 day. Anemia is a hangover in solving digestive problems.

In nervous (neurosis) for a week after each meal, eat half a quince piece steamed with honey. If you are allergic to honey, you can mix it with a spoonful of quince jam.

According to the beneficial properties contained in the fruit, it helps to calm the nerve. 5 gr as a remedy for softening the intestinal tract (remedium enterosolubile). take quince seeds, put 1 liter of boiling water on top and boil for 5 minutes drink the resulting glue 3 times a day.

Application of Quince in cosmetology:

At the skin is lubricated (dermatoliposis): rub a piece of quince on a grater and wipe the skin of the face with the resulting juice, rinse in warm water after 15 minutes. This fruit lasion prevents oiliness on oily facial skin.

In acne out (hyperacnia): scrape off a piece of quince on a grater, rub the finished porridge flat on the moistened facial skin. After 15 minutes, rinse in warm water.

On the skin of the face taken by the sun (dermatothermoplegia): 100 ml of quince seeds. let it brew in boiling water and shake for 5 minutes. Then pass the mixture through the gauze and lightly wipe the surface of the reddened skin. A mixture made from Quince seeds, according to its peculiarity, whitens the skin and restores the condition of meioria.

Mix 1 egg white with an equal amount of quince juice (*sirupus Cydoniae*), water of cologne (*aqua pro perfume*), camphor alcohol (*spiritus camphorates*) to wipe the skin of the face. After 15 minutes, rinse in warm water. Such a mask is used to whiten the skin of the face and free from various characteristic rashes.

In skin burns (combustion cutis): 5 gr. quince seeds 500 ml. put in water and boil for 10 minutes, dip the gauze in the place where the finished lasion was burned.

Healing properties of Quince:

- medication has antibacterial and anti-wound effects;

- used as cholerytic and diuretic;
- has a positive effect on the psyche, improves mood;
- the risk of developing cancer is reduced due to the antioxidants contained in the fruit;
- useful during stress and depression;
- useful for the prevention and treatment of anemia;
- useful in diseases of the gastrointestinal tract;
- useful in diarrhea;
- reduces cholesterol in the blood;
- has a bloodstainer effect;
- has absorbent properties;
- cleanses the body of toxins;
- acute respiratory viral infections and influenza epidemic will help;
- raises immunity;
- applied for treatment when vitamin deficiency;
- used in milk disease;
- prevents aging of the body;
- prevents nausea and being on the dice;
- improves appetite;
- loses bad smell;
- the cornea of the eye is used in inflamed (conjunctivitis);
- used in heart disease;

Side effects of Quince:

- in the acute period of gastritis;
- in the stomach ulcer;
- frequent constipation;
- in colitis and pleuritis;
- in an allergic reaction from the fluffy coating of the bark;
- with cholelithiasis;
- Quince fruit is not recommended for babies, nursing mothers.

Interesting facts about quince fruit:

1. Turkey is the leading producer of Quince fruit.
2. Quince fruit can live without water for a long time.
3. The world's largest quince weighs 5 kg. as it turns out.
4. 10% of cooked Quince consists of sugar.
5. 20% of Quince fruit beans are made up of mucus.
6. The goddess of love, the Aphrodite, called Quince the fruit of passion.
7. In the Middle East, Quince seeds were boiled and used as a medicine against angina, ulcers, sore throat.
8. In his time, Shakespeare also appreciated Quince as an ointment against disorders of gastric activity.
9. In Abu Ali ibn Sina's "Medical exhortations" ("Tibbiyot o'gitalari"), one hundred and one traits of Quince are listed.
10. In Mahmud Qoshgari's "Volume turkish dictionary" ("Devoni lug'atit turk"), Quince was mentioned in the form of "Ayva".

Conclusion: this article talks about the beneficial properties of the quince plant -one in a million representatives of folk medicine, which has passed the test of centuries, which our ancestors are using profitably, but, being forgotten by young people growing up under the influence of modern medicine. The aim is to promote a healthy lifestyle, insisting on abstinence from drugs and supplements that are currently being produced in different countries and filling the pharmacies of our country. We call on the centuries-old heritage of our wise people to be adequately conveyed to generations and effectively applied in practice.

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